

Ministry of Education, Culture and
Science of the Netherlands

ONLINE WORKSHOP ON
HERITAGE IMPACT ASSESSMENT
7, 14 & 21 May 2022

ASSIGNMENT REPORT

The Historic Mosque City of Bagerhat
Group No. 3

Joarder Hafiz Ullah
Md Nawrose Fatemi
Md Nazmul Hassan
Naheed Sultana
Orpita Chowdhury

DISCLAIMER

This assignment has been adapted using the tools included in the upcoming *Guidance and Toolkit for Impact Assessment in a World Heritage Context*.

Participants are instructed to cover the outcome of the workshop exercise under the given content; No need to produce any additional content.

CONTENT

1. Summary of Value and Attribute from SOUV/ Breakdown of SOUV.....	p. 3-5
1.1 Summarized Table of Values & Attributes	
2. Project summary (proposed interventions)	p. 5-7
2.1 5-star Heritage Eco-resort	
2.2 Facilities and Infrastructure for Highway Bus stoppage	
3. Key impacts/concerns.....	p.7-9
4. Preliminary evaluation of key impacts/concerns along with Mitigation suggestions.....	p.10-11
4.1 Mitigation recommendation 1	
4.2 Mitigation recommendation 2	
4.3 Mitigation recommendation 3	
4.4 Mitigation recommendation 4	
4.5 Mitigation recommendation 5	
5. Appendixes (<i>can be submitted as separate documents</i>)	p.12-15
5.1 Tool 1: Values and attributes	
5.2 Tool 2: Potential impacts	
5.3 Tool 3: Evaluation of impact	

List of figures:

Figure 1. Illustrative Map of Historic Map City of Bagerhaat.....	p.3
Figure 2. Illustrative Map of Proposed Development.....	p.5
Figure 3. 3D illustrations of proposed 5-star Heritage Eco-resort.....	p.6
Figure 4. Illustrations of proposed activities for visitors.....	p.6
Figure 5. Illustrations of proposed Highway Bus stoppage.....	p.7
Figure 6: Proposed relocation of new bus stop and alternative access to new 5-star Eco Resort.....	p.10

List of Tables:

Table 1. Summarized Table of Value & Attributes.....	p.4-5
Table 2. Identified potential impact on each attribute of the site	p.7-8
Table 3. Analysis of Potential impacts from the new development/ interventions on the identified Attributes of the site.....	p.8-9
Table 4: Evaluation of potential impacts and proposed alternative action.....	p.10

1. Summary of Value and Attribute from SOUV/ Breakdown of SOUV

Situated in the suburbs of Bagerhat, at the meeting-point of the Ganges and Brahmaputra rivers, this ancient city, formerly known as Khalifatabad, was founded by the Turkish general Ulugh Khan Jahan in the 15th century. The city's infrastructure reveals considerable technical skill and an exceptional number of mosques and early Islamic monuments, many built of brick, can be seen there.

Figure 1. Illustrative Map of Historic Map City of Bagerhaat

The Historic Mosque City of Bagerhat is an important evidence of medieval city in the south-west part of present Bagerhat district which is located in the south-west part of Bangladesh, at the meeting point of the Ganges and Brahmaputra rivers.

The magnificent city, which extended for 50 km², contains some of the most significant buildings of the initial period of the development of Muslim architecture of Bengal which

include 360 mosques, public buildings, mausoleums, bridges, roads, water tanks and other public buildings constructed from baked brick.

This old city, created within a few years and covered up by the jungle after the death of its founder in 1459, is striking because of certain uncommon features.

The density of Islamic religious monuments is explained by the piety of Khan Jahan, which is evidenced by the engraved inscription on his tomb. The lack of fortifications is attributable to the possibilities of retreat into the impenetrable mangrove swamps of the Sundarbans. The monuments, which have been partially disengaged from the vegetation, may be divided into two principal zones 6.5 km apart: to the West, around the mosque of Shait-Gumbad and to the East, around the mausoleum of Khan Jahan. More than 50 monuments have been catalogued: in the first group, the mosques of Singar, Bibi Begni and Clumakkola; and in the second, the mosques of Reza Khoda, Zindavir and Ranvijoypur.

The site has been inscribed in the World Heritage List since 1985 for its exhibition of a unique architectural style, known as Khan-e-Jahan (15th Century A.D.), which is the only known example in the history of architecture, under criterion (iv) as following-

Criterion (iv): The Historic Mosque City of Bagerhat represents the vestiges of a medieval Muslim town in the northern peripheral land of the Sundarbans. It contains some of the most significant buildings of the initial period of the development of Muslim architecture in Bengal. Shait-Gumbad is one of the largest mosques and represents the flavor of the traditional orthodox mosque plan and it is the only example of its kind in the whole of Bengal. The second important monument, Khan Jahan's tomb, is an extraordinary representation of this type of architecture as well as calligraphic parlance.

(UNESCO, 1985, Dossier: 321)

1.1 Summarized Table of Values & Attributes:

Level of recognition	Heritage / Conservation values	Attributes	Sources of information
OUV	Flourished in the 15th century AD, the Historic Mosque City of Bagerhat is an important evidence of medieval ancient city that contains some of the most significant buildings of the initial period of the development of Muslim architecture of Bengal.	The city include 360 mosques, public buildings, mausoleums, bridges, roads, water tanks and other public buildings constructed from baked brick. Use and Function (Living site)	(UNESCO, 1985, Dossier: 321)
	This old city reveals a perfect mastery of the techniques of planning, a will towards spatial organization and a unique architectural style, known as Khan-e-Jahan (15th Century A.D.), which is the only known example in the history of architecture especially in Muslim architecture of Bengal.	All these religious buildings are either profusely embellished with beautiful terracotta floral panels or richly relieved with stone carvings. Settings/ Master plan (water body, layout, approach)	
		Some of the original features are- the stone pillars inside the mosques, reticulated windows, pediment, upper band of cornice. Construction Technique (Lime moter, Dome, Arch, carved cornice etc.)	

	<p>The mosque of Shait-Gumbad, is one of the largest mosques and represents the flavour of the traditional orthodox mosque plan and it is the only example of its kind in Muslim architecture of Bengal.</p>	<p>77 squat domes with 7 four-sided pitched Bengali domes, the vast prayer hall with 11 arched doorways on east and 7 each on north and south, 60 slender stone columns, slightly tapering walls, eleven mihrabs at west wall, along with hollow and round, almost detached corner towers, resembling the bastions of fortress</p> <p>Architectural Characteristics of Khalifatabad (scale, proportion, dome, archway)</p>	
	<p>The mausoleum of Khan Jahan is an extraordinary representation of tomb architecture as well as calligraphic parlance for Muslim architecture of Bengal.</p>	<p>The density of Islamic religious monuments is explained by the piety of Khan Jahan, which is evidenced by the engraved inscription on Khan Jahan's tomb</p> <p>Material (Brick, stone pillar, Terracotta tile)</p>	

Table 1. Summarized Table of Value & Attributes

2. Project summary (proposed interventions)

This proposed development project consists of two potential proposals:

- 2.1) A 5-star Heritage Eco-resort and
- 2.2) Designing proper structural facilities in the existing Bus stoppage on the highway.

Figure 2. Illustrative Map of Proposed Development

2.1 5-star Heritage Eco-resort (Specific Project Brief):

The resort project is awarded through a competition process which will not only act as a world class sophisticated tourist accommodation premise but will also thrive as a facilitating point to promote and ease the tourist agglomeration around the locality emphasizing the UNESCO WH sites.

Figure 3. 3D illustrations of proposed 5-star Heritage Eco-resort

The 100-acre resort will conserve 50% of its site as natural habitat for its existing eco system. Yet it will be able to host national and international level of conferences accommodating 500 people at a time for any daylong event.

Figure 4. Illustrations of proposed activities for visitors

The Resort will constantly support the forest walk within its conserved area and heritage walk to the adjacent WH sites by providing tourist shuttles.

2.2 Facilities and Infrastructure for Highway Bus stoppage (Specific Project Brief):

A designed bus stoppage with smart technology of digital site navigation and tourist friendly amenities will smooth the commuting system to nearby heritage sites and through the highway.

Figure 5. Illustrations of proposed Highway Bus stoppage

3. Key impacts/concerns

There are several identified potential impacts that may be caused due to the proposed development in the World Heritage Site. The major components of the proposed actions such as- Construction, Operation, Induced Traffic, Temporary or Permanent displacement of local facilities and residents have been identified to have potential impact on the previously identified Attributes (Table 1) of the site.

Attributes	Element of a proposed action that has the potential to cause an impact						
	Construction of New Resort	Construction of New Bus Stop	Operation of New Resort	Operation of New Bus Stop	Traffic due to New Bus Stop	Relocation of Existing facilities	Relocation of Residents
Use and Function (Living Site)		X	X	X	X	X	
Settings / Master plan		X	X	X	X	X	X
Architectural Characteristics of Khalifatabad	X	X			X	X	

Construction Technique	X	X					
Material	X	X			X	X	

Table 2. Identified potential impact on each attribute of the site (X refers to presence of an impact)

Firstly, construction of the new contemporary style 5-star Resort and Bus stop may irreversibly damage the existing historic urban fabric of the Mosque city of Bagerhat. The vibration and pollution during the construction phase may significantly affect the stability of centuries old monuments.

Secondly, increased Tourism due to new development may induce heavy traffic leading to other problem like- excessive noise and air pollution, high waste generation, illegal mobile vendors crowding the heritage property premises, increased vandalism and other crimes etc. Religious facilities of the Heritage site, such as- nearest Mosques may get overwhelmed due to overcrowding.

Thirdly, local small businesses and facilities may get temporarily or permanently displaced causing social disturbance. There is a possibility of local residents getting displaced from their traditional and ancestral roots can hamper the essence of the site where communities and culture is considered the heart of the city.

Following table illustrates the analysis of potential impacts that may respond to specific attributes directly and indirectly-

Attributes	Element of a proposed action that has the potential to cause an impact						
	Construction of New Resort	Construction of New Bus Stop	Operation of New Resort	Operation of New Bus Stop	Traffic due to New Bus Stop	Relocation of Existing facilities	Relocation of Residents
Use and Function (Living Site)		May impact moderately if vibration occur during construction	May have impact on mosques and other heritage facilities due to overcrowding of increased tourists	Increased Noise-Air pollution, Waste generation Mobile Vendors (hawkers)	May hamper accessibility of the tourists in the heritage site	The existing local facilities may displace due to new bus stop construction	
Settings / Master plan	The urban identity of the	The urban identity of the	The number	The unplanned	Increased Noise-Air	The existing facilities	Local people

	New Resort may hamper the historic city fabric of the Area	bus stop may hamper the historic city fabric of the Area	of tourists may be increased , who can reside beside the mosque city.	facilities may be increased surrounding the new development	pollution, Waste Generation, Frequent Road accidents, Mobile Vendors (hawkers).	may be relocated temporarily in other places inside the buffer zone	may be displaced from their ancestral roots.
Architectural Characteristics of Khalifatabad	The contemporary identity of the New Resort may hamper the Architectural Characteristics of the historic city	The contemporary identity of the New Bus stop may hamper the Architectural Characteristics of the historic city			Vandalism may increase due to over-crowding of the tourists	Temporary facilities may be in different architectural character.	
Construction Technique	The contemporary construction technique of the New Resort may hamper the existing historic construction technique of the mosque city	The contemporary construction technique of the New Bus Stop may hamper the existing historic construction technique of the mosque city					
Material	The contemporary material of the New Resort may hamper the material characteristics of the historic city	The contemporary material of the New Bus Stop may hamper the material characteristics of the historic city		May deteriorate the exposed surface of the monuments due to vehicles near the barrier zone	Vandalism may increase due to over-crowding of the tourists	Temporary facilities may be in different material character.	

Table 3. Analysis of Potential impacts from the new development/interventions on the identified Attributes of the site

4. Preliminary evaluation of key impacts/concerns along with Mitigation suggestions:

The potential impacts which may directly and indirectly affect the attributes of the heritage site have been further evaluated based on their Reversibility, Duration, Frequency, Nature of Change, Degree of Change and Quality of Change on attributes to generate alternative action proposals that may aid to reduce to an acceptable level if not avoid potential heavy or negative impact.

Attribute	Element of proposed action	Description of potential impact	Reversibility of impact	Duration of impact	Frequency of impact	Nature of change on attribute	Degree of change on attribute	Quality of change on attribute	Evaluation of impact
			Reversible/irreversible	Short-term/long-term	Once/intermittent/continuous	Permanent/temporary change	None/negligible/some/large change	Positive/negative change	Neutral/moderate/major impact
Use and Function	Relocation of proposed bus stop from the buffer zone	Disturbance to life ways and social patterns of local community through increased traffic, noise and air pollution	Irreversible	Long-term	Continuous	Permanent change	Large change	Negative change	Major
Settings/ Master plan	Limitation of the total number of daily visitors	Disturbance to historic setting and deterioration of existing monuments through mass tourism and increased number of vehicles	Irreversible	Long-term	Intermittent	Temporary change	Large change	Negative change	Major
Architectural Characteristics of Khalifatabad	Consideration of necessary facilities in the proposed master plan	Substantial damage to urban fabric due to relocated and temporary facilities	Reversible	Short-term	Intermittent	Temporary change	Some change	Negative change	Moderate
Construction Technique	Consideration of architectural characteristics and integration of existing construction technique of the historic city during design phase and construction phase of new development	Substantial damage to contemporary construction technique and cause visual dysphoria due to urban and contemporary identity of the new development	Irreversible	Long-term	Once	Permanent change	Large change	Negative change	Major
Material	Preparation guidelines for vehicular movement within the buffer zone and introduction of strict code of conduct for the visitors	Deterioration of the exposed surface of the monuments due to increased number of vehicles near the buffer zone and possible vandalism due to mass crowding	Reversible	Short-term	Continuous	Permanent change	Some change	Negative change	Moderate

Table 4: Evaluation of potential impacts and proposed alternative action.

4.1 Mitigation recommendation 1

The bus stop may be relocated away from the heritage premise and buffer zone to minimise the negative impacts discussed earlier. Additionally, alternative access to the resort may be introduced to reduce impact on the main highway that cuts through the city with notable monuments on both sides. This alternative can be effective during construction phase as a better material transportation route as well as for visitors during the operation phase.

Figure 6: Proposed relocation of new bus stop and alternative access to new 5-star Eco Resort.

4.2 Mitigation recommendation 2

As a city with significant historic value, the historic Mosque city of Bagerhat needs strict policies for the tourism sector. Potential new development will definitely attract tourists in the near future, which is analysed to cause heavy impact on the site, especially the monuments. Limiting the number of visitors per day, as adopted worldwide in many heritage sites can be a better solution to maintain a balance between conservation and economic development of the city.

4.3 Mitigation recommendation 3

It is important to pay close attention to the needs of the local communities when developments occur in significant historic cities like Bagerhat. Often communities inherently oppose such developments because in most cases it is the community who get affected the most. Local small businesses end up getting displaced to accommodate new development and even to maintain the 5-star status after the construction phase. In some cases, even communities get temporarily or permanently displaced from their traditional and ancestral roots causing potential social disturbance and emotional trauma. Even though, communities are compensated with money or resettlements, a better solution is to consider the community in design phase and accommodate the local businesses and facilities within the new development to avoid clash with community and resulting temporary and illegal structures that may hamper the urban fabric and overall serenity of the site.

4.4 Mitigation recommendation 4

As a historic city, Bagerhat has its unique architectural characteristics in the form of material, construction techniques and style, which gives it the well-deserved heritage status in the world heritage list. It is absolutely necessary that this specific attribute is taken most seriously in the design phase of the development. As the proposed development is a modern structure with modern facilities, its contemporary presence in the historic setting may cause severe visual dysphoria. Protection of the urban fabric and historic setting is a non-negotiable aspect in this case. Hence, the design and function proposal of the development must be revisited with this consideration.

4.5 Mitigation recommendation 5

With a flourishing tourism sector and changes that may come with the new development project, there must be certain guidelines for the local authorities and visitors such as- vehicular and pedestrian movement, code of conduct in the heritage premises to enhance the experience of the visitors while maintaining sensitivity and respect for the heritage and history that belongs to the community.

5. Appendixes

5.1 Tool 1: Values and attributes

Level of recognition	Heritage / Conservation values	Attributes	Sources of information
<p>OUV</p>	<p>Flourished in the 15th century AD, the Historic Mosque City of Bagerhat is an important evidence of medieval ancient city that contains some of the most significant buildings of the initial period of the development of Muslim architecture of Bengal.</p>	<p>Use and Function (Living site)</p> <p>The city include 360 mosques, public buildings, mausoleums, bridges, roads, water tanks and other public buildings constructed from baked brick.</p>	<p>(UNESCO, 1985, Dossier: 321)</p>
	<p>This old city reveals a perfect mastery of the techniques of planning, a will towards spatial organization and a unique architectural style, known as Khan-e-Jahan (15th Century A.D.), which is the only known example in the history of architecture especially in Muslim architecture of Bengal.</p>	<p>Settings/ Master plan (water body, layout, approach)</p> <p>All these religious buildings are either profusely embellished with beautiful terracotta floral panels or richly relieved with stone carvings.</p>	
	<p>The mosque of Shait-Gumbad, is one of the largest mosques and represents the flavour of the traditional orthodox mosque plan and it is the only example of its kind in Muslim architecture of Bengal.</p>	<p>Construction Technique (Lime moter, Dome, Arch, carved cornice etc.)</p> <p>Some of the original features are- the stone pillars inside the mosques, reticulated windows, pediment, upper band of cornice.</p>	
	<p>The mosque of Shait-Gumbad, is one of the largest mosques and represents the flavour of the traditional orthodox mosque plan and it is the only example of its kind in Muslim architecture of Bengal.</p>	<p>Architectural Characteristics of Khalifatabad (scale, proportion, dome, archway)</p> <p>77 squat domes with 7 four-sided pitched Bengali domes, the vast prayer hall with 11 arched doorways on east and 7 each on north and south, 60 slender stone columns, slightly tapering walls, eleven mihrabs at west wall, along with hollow and round, almost detached corner towers, resembling the bastions of fortress</p>	
	<p>The mausoleum of Khan Jahan is an extraordinary representation of tomb architecture as well as calligraphic parlance for Muslim architecture of Bengal.</p>	<p>Material (Brick, stone pillar, Terracotta tile)</p> <p>The density of Islamic religious monuments is explained by the piety of Khan Jahan, which is evidenced by the engraved inscription on Khan Jahan's tomb</p>	

5.2 Tool 2: Potential impacts

Attributes	Element of a proposed action that has the potential to cause an impact						
	Construction of New Resort	Construction of New Bus Stop	Operation of New Resort	Operation of New Bus Stop	Traffic due to New Bus Stop	Relocation of Existing facilities	Relocation of Residents
Use and Function (Living Site)		May impact moderately if vibration occur during construction	May have impact on mosques and other heritage facilities due to overcrowding of increased tourists	Increased Noise-Air pollution, Waste generation Mobile Vendors (hawkers)	May hamper accessibility of the tourists in the heritage site	The existing local facilities may be displaced due to new bus stop construction	
Settings / Master plan	The urban identity of the New Resort may hamper the historic city fabric of the Area	The urban identity of the bus stop may hamper the historic city fabric of the Area	The number of tourists may be increased, who can reside beside the mosque city.	The unplanned facilities may be increased surrounding the new development	Increased Noise-Air pollution, Waste generation Frequent Road accidents, Mobile Vendors (hawkers).	The existing facilities may be relocated temporarily in other places inside the buffer zone	Local people may be displaced from their ancestral roots.
Architectural Characteristics of Khalifatabad	The contemporary identity of the New Resort may hamper the Architectural Characteristics of the historic city	The contemporary identity of the New Bus stop may hamper the Architectural Characteristics of the historic city			Vandalism may increase due to overcrowding of the tourists	Temporary facilities may be in different architectural character.	
Construction Technique	The contemporary construction technique of the New Resort may	The contemporary construction technique of the New Bus Stop may					

	hamper the existing historic construction technique of the mosque city	hamper the existing historic construction technique of the mosque city					
Material	The contemporary material of the New Resort may hamper the material characteristics of the historic city	The contemporary material of the New Bus Stop may hamper the material characteristics of the historic city		May deteriorate the exposed surface of the monuments due to vehicles near the barrier zone	Vandalism may increase due to over-crowding of the tourists	Temporary facilities may be in different material character.	

5.3 Tool 3: Evaluation of impact

Attribute	Element of proposed action	Description of potential impact	Reversibility of Impact	Duration of Impact	Frequency of Impact	Nature of change on attribute	Degree of change on attribute	Quality of change on attribute	Evaluation of impact
			Reversible/ Irreversible	Short-term/ long-term	Once/ intermittent/ continuous	Permanent/ temporary change	None/ negligible/ some/ large change	Positive/ negative change	Neutral/ minor/ moderate/ major impact (neg & pos)
Use and Function (Living site)	Relocation of proposed bus stop from the barrier zone	Disturbance to lifeways and social patterns of local community through increased traffic, noise and air pollution	Irreversible	Long-term	Continuous	Permanent change	Large change	Negative change	
Settings/ Masterplan (waterbody, layout, approach)	Limitation of the total number of daily visitors	Disturbance to historic setting and deterioration of existing monuments through mass tourism and increased number of vehicles	Irreversible	Long-term	Intermittent	Temporary change	Large change	Negative change	
Architectural Characteristics of Khalifatabad (scale, proportion, dome, archway)	Consideration of necessary facilities in the proposed master plan	Substantial damage to urban fabric due to relocated and temporary facilities	Reversible	Short-term	Intermittent	Temporary change	Some change	Negative change	
Construction Technique (Lime mortar, Dome, Arch, carved cornice etc.	Consideration of architectural characteristics and integration of existing construction technique of the historic city during design phase and construction of new development	Substantial damage to contemporary construction technique and cause visual dysphoria due to urban and contemporary identity of the new development	Irreversible	Long-term	Once	Permanent change	Large change	Negative change	
Material (Brick, stone pillar, Terracotta tile)	Preparation guidelines for vehicular movement within the buffer zone and introduction of strict code of conduct for the visitors	Deterioration of the exposed surface of the monuments due to increased number of vehicles near the barrier zone and possible vandalism due to mass crowding	Reversible	Short-term	Continuous	Permanent change	Some change	Negative change	